

LAST YEARS PEACE AGREEMENTS BETWEEN ISRAEL AND ARAB COUNTRIES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON REGIONAL TOURISM

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Abstract: *Israel's relations with Arab Middle East states have undergone many significant upheavals, and over the years have fluctuated between bitter, bloody wars and covert cooperation. The peace agreement with Egypt widened the spectrum even further and opened the door to official civil and economic partnerships. Advances in peace negotiations with Palestinians in the 1990s brought about a peace treaty with Jordan, and even led to a short blossoming of relations between Israel and other Arab states. Unfortunately, there still no enough trust between Israel and Arab countries to promote tourism between them, since local communities feel uneasy to treat Israel as a friend and prefer to wait.*

Key words: *Peace agreements, international relations, tourism.*

ACORDURI DE PACE DIN ANI ULTIMI ÎNTRE ISRAEL ȘI ȚĂRILE ARABE ȘI INFLUENȚA LOR ASUPRA TURISMULUI REGIONAL

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Rezumat: *Relațiile Israelului cu țările arabe din Orientul Mijlociu au suferit schimbări majore, oscilând între războaie sângeroase ireconciliabile și cooperare deschisă. Acordul de pace cu Egiptul a extins și mai mult spațiul de interacțiune și a deschis ușa pentru cooperarea civilă și economică. Progresul în negocierile de pace cu Autoritatea Palestiniană în anii 1990 a condus la un acord de pace cu Iordania și la o relație înfloritoare între Israel și țările arabe. Din păcate, Israelul și țările lumii arabe nu au construit și consolidat legăturile turistice, deoarece multe comunități locale nu sunt pregătite să fie prietenoase cu Israelul și preferă să aștepte.*

Cuvinte cheie: *tratate de pace, relații internaționale, turism.*

INTRODUCTION

Israel's relations with Middle East states have undergone many significant upheavals, and over the years have fluctuated between bitter, bloody wars and covert cooperation. The peace agreement with Egypt widened the spectrum even further and opened the door to official civil and economic partnerships. Advances in peace negotiations with Palestinians in the 1990s brought about a peace treaty with Jordan, and even led to a short blossoming of relations between Israel and other Arab states. This period ended with the second intifada and the wars in Gaza [1].

The first country in the Arab countries to sign a peace agreement was Egypt, which led to economic cooperation. After that, a peace agreement was signed with Jordan in the 1990s and there were many others in 2010-2020s, after replacement of authorities in Arab countries due to the Arab spring, and due to Iran's unclear threat to the stability of the region positioning it as a common makeup of these countries with Israel [1].

2020S PEACE AGREEMENTS BETWEEN ISRAEL AND ARAB COUNTRIES

The NETANYAHU government which refrained from advancing negotiations with the Palestinians, began to argue that it allowed progress to normalize with Arab states even without progressing in the peace process with the Palestinians.

Lately, peace agreements were signed with the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, Bahrain, Morocco, Qatar [3], and a cooperation was promoted without a peace agreement with Saudi Arab [1].

The collaborations are not only limited to the intelligence and security field, but also to the economic field. Cooperation in the field of tourism takes place with countries legitimized by agreements.

The first Arab countries to sign peace agreements with Israel were Egypt and Jordan, and over the years we have seen the arrival of tourists to Israel and vice versa, but the barrier still existed and not many Arab tourists came to Israel because it was still the general boycott from the side of most Arab countries towards Israel [1, 2].

On the other hand, many Israeli tourists began to go and visit these countries, especially Egypt, when most of them went to the Sinai area, which is a tourist area and quite safe compared to other places in Egypt. And a lot of Israeli Arab citizens visited Egypt and Jordan, where they have relatives.

TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

After the signing of the recent peace agreements in the last decade with other Arab countries such as Qatar, the United Arab Emirates, Morocco, Bahrain, Kuwait, the feeling that we suffer less from a boycott and Arab tourists began to visit the State of Israel which in the past they were afraid to do because there was still a boycott from most Arab countries [2].

On the other hand, many Israelis have also started visiting these countries, which is a new and interesting destination for them that offers new attractions, now that there are not many barriers and less boycott when most Arab countries have signed peace and normalization agreements with Israel and will be able to visit Israel and also the opposite when Israeli tourists can visit Arab countries, you have to offer and highlight the important things from a tourist point of view that can attract more tourists to visit in both directions when there is no shortage of special things in the State of Israel and especially that there is a religious city of Jerusalem. For Arabs to come and visit it [2].

And from here it is necessary to highlight and market these places in a correct way that will get the Arab tourist interested and visit here , and at the same time work on the psychological and social barriers that still interfere [1].

There are not many tourists from Arab countries in the Middle East visiting the State of Israel and the reasons for this are, among other things, psychological barriers and the boycott of Arab countries with which there are no peace agreements and also because of the Palestinian issue.

The State of Israel has the "diagnostic policy" procedure and it applies to tourists from Arab countries who wish to come and visit the State of Israel. This procedure means that tourists from Arab countries who wish to come to Israel must send an application before the security officials discuss their application before their visa to Israel is approved and this makes it difficult for them to visit the State of Israel because this process takes months and it leads to frustration and despair. This is one of the problematic things that prevents the realization of the tourism potential

For example, in 2018, the number of Egyptian tourists who visited the State of Israel was only about 6,200 tourists [2]. The number of Egyptian tourists is even smaller compared to about 400,000 Israeli tourists who visited Egypt this year, it is likely that the majority visited Sinai. The agreement with the Union of Emirates and the recent Abraham Accords is a great opportunity to shatter the psychological barriers and enable meetings between citizens of Arab countries and citizens of Israel and to develop the tourism industry in a very good way.

The State of Israel has tremendous potential for some of the best and most sought-after tourist places in the world. The very fact that the potential exists and the places are there then the problem for the Arab tourist to get to Israel is not the lack of places or the lack of attractions, and if you look at it then in general the State of Israel has the most touristic places and one of the holiest places for Islam - the Holy City of Jerusalem that has one of the holy places for Islam and Christians and every Arab would like to go to them and visit them. Jerusalem is the holy city for all peoples and Arabs especially and they will want to come visit it and see the holy places that are related to their religion and culture. Israel also has one of the most beautiful tourist cities in the world, this is Eilat, there is also the Dead Sea and there is also the Golan Heights and there is the “city without a break”, Tel Aviv. There is no doubt that the potential of tourist places in the State of Israel is one of the best in the world, but as mentioned before, the main barrier that prevents a large wave of tourism to Israel from Arab countries is the psychological barrier and fear of boycott from the Arab world [2].

On the other hand, which is the side of the Israeli tourist, there is also the psychological barrier that greatly hinders the Israeli tourist from visiting Arab countries. The psychological fear is that the Israeli tourist fears that the Arabs will harm him because he is a Jew and the thought that these two peoples are enemies still prevents the number of Israeli tourists from visiting Arab countries. I gave earlier for example that large numbers of Israeli tourists visited Egypt and most of them visited Sinai and not Cairo or another city in Egypt and it shows that the Israeli tourist likes to spend time in tourist areas in Arab countries that have interesting attractions but do not want friction with Arab citizens. Compared to Cairo or other cities in Egypt and this shows the barrier we talked about earlier and it is the psychological fear [2].

SUMMARY

The culture and tourism fields of international cooperation between Israel and Arab countries has potential, but unfortunately is not developing as quickly as it could be. Egypt is the best example for this phenomena. Although there are diplomatic relations and peace agreement, there are still only few cultural and tourism relations. Egypt tourism agents not once tried to initiate cooperation like tourism cruises including Israel and Egypt, common international conferences and arts and music events, however they still cope with possible uneasiness of local community to accept Israel as a friend, and they prefer to wait.

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